

Matooke Food Target Product Profile Workplan, at NARL-Uganda

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Ethics: The activities, which led to the production of this document, were assessed and approved by the CIRAD Ethics Committee (H2020 ethics self-assessment procedure). When relevant, samples were prepared according to good hygiene and manufacturing practices. When external participants were involved in an activity, they were priorly informed about the objective of the activity and explained that their participation was entirely voluntary, that they could stop the interview at any point and that their responses would be anonymous and securely stored by the research team for research purposes.

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ABSTRACT

The RTBfoodomics project officially started with a kickoff and planning meeting organized at CIAT (Cali, Colombia) in March 2025. This gathering brought together the partners of the project to align on project activities and responsibilities. Defining a standard sampling protocol was of particular importance.

Following the meeting, NARL produced a detailed workplan outlining the genotypes to be harvested and the samples to be produced and analyzed. The sampling protocol was discussed at length to ensure enough replications of each genotype were included in the workplans (at planting, harvesting and sample preparation).

When cooked, the East African Highland Cooking bananas (EAHCB), also known as matooke is characterized by a unique insipid taste and aroma, golden yellow colour and a tender texture. These attributes have endeared an EAHCB meal to consumers and constitute the unique quality described as ‘tookeness’, originating from the term ‘matooke’ used to describe a cooked meal of the EAHCB. Consumers look for these attributes in the hybrids. Hybrids that lack this quality are often rejected. Most of the banana hybrids developed so far have been rated by consumers as inferior to EAHCB with respect to nearly all sensory attributes implying that they lack the ‘tookeness’ qualities. As already reported in other studies, the ‘tookeness’ quality could be associated with a set of metabolites present or absent in the banana genotypes. The specific metabolites associated with ‘tookeness’ quality are not known. The proposed research seeks to unravel the ‘tookeness’ quality through profiling the metabolites and flavor profiles associated with the unique taste and aroma of matooke bananas. This will be achieved by selecting 15 genotypes from among the high-, intermediate-, and low-quality groups for this study. All samples will be sourced from the established breeding and germplasm collection fields at the National Agricultural Research Laboratories (NARL) in Kawanda, central Uganda.

The selected genotypes have already been phenotyped for texture, color, aroma and flavor -traits identified as key drivers of matooke hybrid preference using SOPs developed the phase I of the RTBFoods project. For each genotype, ten plants have been planted in each of two replications. A total of 20 plants per genotype are, therefore, available. Sampling will occur within the same season and at the same physiological maturity for each genotype. It is important to note that matooke genotypes vary in their maturity ages; therefore, harvesting will be staggered based on each genotype’s specific maturity timeline. To minimize variability, only fingers from the 2nd and 3rd clusters of each bunch will be used for sampling.

Fully matured bunches will be harvested from the 20 plants available from each genotype. Six representative bunches will be selected to serve as the six biological replicates required for this study. From each of those representative bunches, fingers from the 2nd and 3rd clusters will be taken. Fingers from the 4th cluster may be included when bunches are too small, and not enough material can be obtained from the 2nd and 3rd clusters alone.

All fingers from a given bunch will be thoroughly mixed together and then randomly split into two groups, which would be respectively used as samples for raw and cooked tissue. The fingers will then be peeled, sliced into small pieces of tissue, freeze-dried and transported to Holloway, UK for metabolite analysis. Cooked samples of the second group will be used for flavor trapping. The traps will be shipped to CIRAD for flavor profiling.

Key Words: Matooke, Tookeness, EAHCB (East African Highland Cooking Bananas), Hybrids, Metabolites, Flavor profiling, Genotypes, Texture, Aroma, Sampling

1 PHENOTYPING SAMPLES

Figure 1 presents the key terminology used throughout this report to enhance understanding and minimize potential misinterpretations. Fifteen genotypes (described in Section 2) were selected from among high-, intermediate-, and low-quality groups for this study. These genotypes will be phenotyped for texture, color, aroma, and flavor—traits identified as key drivers of matooke hybrid preference (Marimo et al., 2019; Akankwasa et al., 2021).

*Figure 1: Illustration of the fruiting structure of banana and plantains. All fruits in a plant develop in a **bunch** around a common stem. Different **clusters** of fruits grow along this common stem. Within a given cluster a **hand** of fruits can be separated. Each hand has several **fingers** or fruits.*

1.1 Phenotyping using harmonized SOPs: Core traits

Texture profiles will be evaluated using **(a)** sensory methods—including Quantitative Descriptive Analysis and Consumer Preference Testing—as outlined in the published protocol by Nowakunda et al. (2019), and **(b)** instrumental texture profiling, following the protocol established for matooke texture analysis by Nowakunda et al. (2023).

The **colour profile** of the samples will be evaluated using **(a)** sensory methods—including Quantitative Descriptive Analysis and Consumer Preference Testing—following a published standard operating protocol for matooke sensory evaluation (Nowakunda et al., 2019), and **(b)** instrumental methods using chroma, based on the established matooke color analysis protocol (Nowakunda et al., 2024). At NARL, Uganda, **aroma and flavor** will be assessed using published sensory methods (Nowakunda et al., 2019). An overview of the complete sampling and phenotyping process is illustrated in **Figure 2**.

1.2 Instrumental phenotyping for aroma and flavor

Samples for flavor and aroma analysis will be harvested by selecting bunches and fingers as described in Section 3 and **Figure 2**. Approximately 500 g of raw pulp from the selected fingers will be immediately immersed in liquid nitrogen and transported to the laboratory for freeze-drying. The freeze-dried samples will be stored at -20 °C until shipment to CIRAD for flavor and aroma analysis. The same procedure will be applied to samples of ready-to-eat matooke.

1.3 Other traits to phenotype

In addition to the core traits related to matooke quality, additional data—such as Rapid Visco Analyzer (RVA) parameters, solubility, dry matter content (DMC), and starch content—will be collected from uncooked samples (see **Figure 2**).

1.4 Environmental/physiological conditions during the phenotyping process

All samples will be sourced from the established breeding and germplasm collection fields at the National Agricultural Research Laboratories (NARL) in Kawanda, central Uganda. For each genotype, ten plants have been planted in each of two replications. A total of 20 plants per genotype are, therefore, available. Sampling will occur within the same season and at the same physiological maturity for each genotype. It is important to note that matooke genotypes vary in their maturity ages; therefore, harvesting will be staggered based on each genotype's specific maturity timeline. To minimize variability, only fingers from the 2nd and 3rd clusters of each bunch (**Figure 1**) will be used for sampling.

2 DEFINITION OF GENOTYPES TO SCREEN

The genotypes selected for this study were chosen from over 100 previously phenotyped genotypes (Akankwasa et al., 2021) based on evaluations of color and texture (using both instrumental and sensory methods), as well as aroma and flavor (assessed using sensory methods only). The selection focused on identifying genotypes with clearly contrasting phenotypes and varying levels of end-user acceptance. The genotypes were categorized into three groups: (1) highly preferred genotypes, designated as **Good**; (2) acceptable genotypes, designated as **Intermediate**; and (3) rejected or unacceptable genotypes, designated as **Poor** (**Table 1**). A key objective during the kickoff meeting was to define a germplasm set that would maximize the likelihood of capturing meaningful contrasts in core traits at the time of harvesting and processing.

Table 1: List of fifteen genotypes selected for texture, colour, aroma and flavor phenotypic and metabolomics analysis.

	Good quality	Intermediate quality	Poor quality
1	Nakitembe	Nfuuka	NARITA 11
2	Mbwazirume	NARITA 7	NARITA 13
3	Kibuzi	NARITA17	917K-2
4	Mpologoma	NAROBAN 4	365K-1
5	Enzirabahima	NAROBAN 5	9128-3

2.1 Brief description of the genotypes to screen

The genotypes Nakitembe, Mbwazirume, Kibuzi, Mpologoma, Enzirabahima, and Nfuuka are popular landrace cultivars belonging to the East African Highland Banana (EAHB) subgroup—a classification for triploid cooking and beer bananas (Lejju et al., 2006). These cultivars thrive in highland regions at elevations between 1,400 and 2,000 meters and are found exclusively in East Africa. It is believed that they originated

in Southeast Asia and were introduced to East Africa by Arab traders around 4000 B.C. Since then, they have undergone significant evolution through natural mutations and user-driven selection, making East Africa a recognized center of secondary diversity for these bananas (Lejju et al., 2005). All EAHB cultivars belong to the AAA genome group.

The EAHB subgroup accounts for the majority of bananas grown in Uganda and is widely known as matooke, named after the traditional dish prepared by steaming these cooking bananas (Lejju et al., 2006; Neumann & Hildebrandt, 2009). A study of EAHB in Uganda reported over 80 phenotypically distinct cultivars, a diversity largely attributed to natural mutations and farmer-led selection (Karamura, 1996). **Tables 2a** and **2b** summarize the available information on the quality traits of the 15 genotypes selected for this study.

Table 2a: Summary of the germplasm to screen. All material grown in the Central Uganda region.

Genotype	Phenotypic score (QDSA)			Planting	Harvesting	Number of	
	Colour	Texture	Aroma	Date (variable)		Reps	Plants
1. Nakitembe	8.0	1.6	8.1			2	10
2. Mbwazirume	9.0	2.1	8.0			2	10
3. Kibuzi	8.9	1.7	8.8			2	10
4. Mpologoma	8.3	3.1	7.3			2	10
5. Enzirabahima	6.5	3.0	6.7			2	10
6. Nfuuka	7.1	4.9	6.3			2	10
7. NARITA 7	8.0	4.7	6.1			2	10
8. NARITA 17	7.1	4.9	6.4			2	10
9. NAROBAN 4	7.5	3.8	6.2			2	10
10. NAROBAN 5	6.9	3.7	6.3			2	10
11. NARITA 11	6.1	4.6	3.6			2	10
12. NARITA 13	5.2	3.8	3.1			2	10
13. 917-K-2	5.4	3.9	4.3			2	10
14. 365K-1	4.9	4.1	4.1			2	10
15. 9128-3	4.2	4.9	3.7			2	10

Note: QDSA scores: 0 = absent; 10 = Extreme intensity)

The genotypes NARITA 7, NARITA 17, NAROBAN 4, NAROBAN 5, NARITA 11, NARITA 13, 917, 365K-1, and 9128-3 are locally bred lines. These originate from biparental populations developed through crosses between female-fertile EAHB landraces—primarily Kabucuragye, Enzirabahima, Entukura, Nakayonga, Kazirakwe, and Tereza—and non-matooke male diploids such as Calcutta 4 and *M. acuminata burmanica* (Pillay et al., 2001; Ssebuliba et al., 2005; Brown et al., 2017; Batte et al., 2019). More recently, locally bred male parents including 7i6, 2905, 201087-4(AG), TMB2X8075-7, and TMB2X7197-2 have also been used.

In some cases, tetraploid lines such as 660K-1, 222K-1, 1154K-2, 376K-1, 401K-1, and 365K-1 have served as female parents in these breeding efforts. Unfortunately, the female-fertile landrace genotypes used in these crosses are generally unpopular among farmers due to their poor agronomic performance and limited consumer appeal.

Table 3b: Summary of the germplasm to screen (TPA and Chroma). All material grown in the Central Uganda region

Genotype	Phenotypic score			Planting	Harvesting	Number of	
	Colour (b*)	Texture (N)	Aroma	Date (Variable)		Reps	Plants
1.Nakitembe	25.1	1.9	ND			2	10
2.Mbwazirume	29.18	2.3	ND			2	10
3.Kibuzi	27.5	2.4	ND			2	10
4.Mpologoma	27,2	2.3	ND			2	10
5.Enzirabahima	22.5	2.9	ND			2	10
6.Nfuuka	22.1	2.9	ND			2	10
7.NARITA 7	19.7	3.1	ND			2	10
8.NARITA 17	22.1	3.3	ND			2	10
9.NAROBAN 4	20.1	2.9	ND			2	10
10.NAROBAN 5	21.8	3.9	ND			2	10
11.NARITA 11	19.2	4.1	ND			2	10
12.NARITA 13	20.5	4.0	ND			2	10
13.917-K-2	19.8	3.5	ND			2	10
14.365K-1	20.1	4.0	ND			2	10
15.9128-3	19.4	3.9	ND			2	10

2.2 Alternative back-up germplasm or sources of sampling

Different banana genotypes reach maturity at varying times. Even within the same genotype, plants may mature at different rates, despite being planted simultaneously. This variability poses a challenge to obtaining the targeted six biological replicates of each selected genotype ready for sampling at the same time. To address this, alternative genotypes within the same quality categories as the selected ones have been identified as potential substitutes (Table 3).

Table 4: Alternative back-up genotypes to test in case a problem arises during the harvest and/or sampling in any of the initial 15 genotypes described in Table 1

	Good quality	Intermediate quality	Poor quality
1	Musakala	M30	NARITA 21
2	Muvubo	Nakawere	NARITA 15
3	Kisansa	NARITA 24	NARITA 8
4	Nakabululu		NARITA 14
5	Nakyatengu		NARITA 2

3 SAMPLING STRATEGY AND EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

Six biological replicates from each of the 15 contrasting banana genotypes listed in **Table 1** will be obtained. All the replicates from the same genotype will be harvested at the same time but at varying ages for the different genotype taking into consideration their variability in flowering and harvesting age. Alternative

genotypes (**Table 3**) will be sampled in case mature bunches of the originally selected germplasm were not available.

Fully matured bunches (using traditional maturity indicators) will be harvested from the 20 plants available from each genotype (**Figure 2**). Six **representative bunches** will be selected (out of the 20 potentially available) to serve as the six **biological replicates** required for this study. From each of those representative bunches, fingers from the 2nd and 3rd clusters will be taken (refer to **Figure 1** for clarification). Fingers from the 4th cluster may be included when bunches are too small, and not enough material can be obtained from the 2nd and 3rd clusters alone.

All fingers from a given bunch (e.g., those coming from 2nd and 3rd clusters) will be thoroughly mixed together and then **randomly** split into two groups, which would be respectively used as samples for raw and cooked tissue. The fingers will then be peeled (**Figure 2**).

3.1 Handling of uncooked (raw) samples

If necessary, samples may be immersed in liquid nitrogen before transporting them to the lab. After peeling the sub-sample of raw fingers, they will be processed with a blender to generate a **homogenized paste**. From the homogenized paste of raw fingers a few (e.g., 10) and small (e.g., 10-15g of fresh tissue) sub-samples will be randomly scooped out, pooled together, freeze dried and then stored at -20°C pending transportation to Holoway, UK for metabolite analysis (**Figure 2**).

Pectin content may be evaluated in freeze-dried samples as well. This assessment would take place in CIRAD (**Figure 2**).

The rest of the homogenized paste of raw fingers will be used for phenotyping immediately after blending. Phenotyping involves the core instrumental and sensory assessments of texture and colour described in Section # 1 above. Published standard operating procedures (Nowakunda et al., 2019; 2023; 2024) will be followed in this phenotyping process. In addition, the homogenized paste of raw fingers will be analyzed through a rapid viscoanalyzer (RVA) for the standard assessment of pasting properties, and other relevant traits such as solubility, dry matter and starch contents, etc.

3.2 Handling of cooked (ready to eat) samples

Immediately after peeling the sub-sample of fingers to be cooked, they will be handled and cooked following the published standard operating procedure (Nowakunda et al. 2019). Three samples will be taken randomly from the ready to eat matooke from each of the 15 genotypes described in Table 1 (**Figure 2**).

A few (e.g., 10) and small (e.g., 10-15g of freshly cooked matooke) sub-samples will be randomly scooped out, pooled together, freeze dried and stored at -20°C pending transportation to Holoway, UK for metabolite analysis.

A second sub-sample will be treated as described in Section 1.2 and stored at -20°C pending shipment to CIRAD.

The third sub-sample of ready to eat matooke will be used for sensory and instrumental assessment of the core traits described in Section 1.1 (Nowakunda et al., 2019; 2023; 2024)

Figure 2: Sampling strategy to be followed for each of the 15 genotypes to assess. The example illustrates the sampling of fruits from the bunch harvested from the 9th plant (in rep # 1) of genotype # 8.

4 CHRONOGRAM OF ACTIVITIES

The chronology of activities is depicted in Figure 3. Harvest, preparation of samples and phenotyping of the samples will take place between April and September 2025. As stated above, each genotype will be harvested at its own optimum maturity. The shipment of samples for metabolomic analysis at Royal Holloway University of London (London, UK) and those for aroma and flavor at CIRAD (Montpellier, France) will tentatively take place in October 2025.

Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	
			Harvest									
			Sensory and instrumental phenotyping									
			Preparation of samples for CIRAD and RHUL									
									Shipment of samples to RHUL/CIRAD			

APPENDICE

RHUL team feedback

Experimental design and planning is outstanding and compliant with metabolomics guidelines defined in the project. Very much appreciated the efforts in adapting methodology for metabolomics analysis and looking forward to analysing the sample set.

Minor comment is regarding the freeze-drying of raw samples (section 1.3, figure 2). Is the blending step (black step 4, figure 2) necessary? If possible, a random mix of raw (uncooked) slices/cubes (4-6 pieces) from the pool of fingers from 1 bunch could be freeze-dried as intact pieces, i.e, before blending, and then shipped to RHUL. Similar as to the workflow described for the cooked samples. We can grind the freeze-dried tissue here to powder for metabolomics analysis.

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